

Carbon Offsetting Projects

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Soil sampling conducted under the framework of the SUS-SOIL project to estimate soil carbon sequestration across Europe

Carbon offsetting projects are projects aiming at accounting the capacity of carbon sequestration in the tree standing biomass in forest lands that is translated into carbon credits. The accountability of carbon in the conifer and broadleaved stands is based on a series of algorithms or equations estimated by harvesting a series of trees of the same species at different ages. The trees are cut in pieces such as the trunk and large and small branches of different trees to deliver equations that are based in the normal diameter or diameter at breast height to know the current carbon sequestered by a tree in a given moment. The algorithms are also used to predict the capacity of carbon sequestration to appoint a new afforested or reforested area to be sold in the market. When a forest stand is appointed for a Carbon offsetting projects aspects associated to a minimum area to be included as part of the Carbon offsetting projects should be considered. Also the reforestation or afforestation date is relevant because years like 1990 is considered as an starting point for accounting Carbon offsetting projects as the CO₂ to be sequestered has to be linked to pre-industrial times. Moreover, tree species have also to be taken into account, as fast-growing tree species are usually penalized by half due to the short period of carbon sequestration they have, as happened with the *Eucalyptus* in *Spain*. However, forestlands are able to sequester more carbon than that associated with the presence of the trees, like the soil. The capacity of forest to capitalize soils is broadly recognized and intuitively perceived. Forest soil has at least half of the carbon existing in the stand that is not currently under the carbon credit market. The SUS-SOIL project is aiming at quantifying the carbon sequestered in young and old stands that will allow to determine an algorithm to be used as part of the Carbon Offsetting projects and recognized by the FSC.

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**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

